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Use of Ortho-substituted Benzalidine-thiosemicarbazone as Analytical Reagent—Gravimetric Determination of Ni(II)

Y. THAKUR*, J. THAKUR and A. K. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, L. S. College, Muzaffarpur, Bihar University, Muzaffarpur

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DIMETHYLGlyoxime has been used as an analytical reagent for gravimetric analysis of nickel and palladium. The difficulty arises in the determination of nickel in the presence of large amounts of cobalt ion. Also use of excess ammonia causes the dissolution of nickel dimethylglyoxime complex, but the precipitation of Ni(II) with *o*-nitrobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone and *o*-chlorobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone is complete at pH = 8-9. Palladium(II) does not interfere while the precipitation of Co(II), Cu(II) and Fe(III) are prevented by using suitable masking agents.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A. R. grade stock solutions of nickel (1%) was prepared by dissolving nickel sulphate in double distilled water and 1% ethanol solution of the ligands was employed.

Preparation of the Ligands :—(a) *O*-nitrobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone :—*O*-nitrobenzaldehyde was prepared as described in the literature¹.

(b) *O*-chlorobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone :—It was prepared by dissolving *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde in ethanol and treating it with thiosemicarbazide dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid. The ligand was obtained as a pale yellow precipitate. The precipitate was recrystallised from ethanol and dried (m.p. 217°).

Determination of Nickel :—A solution containing known amount of nickel(II) was diluted to 100 ml

* Present address :—Head of the Department of Chemistry, Mithila University, Darbhanga.

and heated to 50-60°. The hot solution was then treated with an ethanol solution of the ligand. The pH was adjusted to 8-9 with dilute ammonia. A brown precipitate (red precipitate in the case of *o*-chlorobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone) was obtained. The whole mass was digested on steam-bath for about half an hour, filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G-4) and washed with hot water and ethanol. The precipitate was dried in an air-oven at 120-130° to constant weight, weighed as Ni(C₈H₇N₄O₂S)₂ and Ni(C₈H₇N₄SCl)₂ respectively in the case of *o*-nitrobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone and *o*-chlorobenzalidinetiosemicarbazone. The complexes are soluble in acetone but insoluble in ethanol and methanol. The results of some of the estimations are tabulated below :—

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Ni(II) AT pH=8-9 : (a) *o*-NITRO-(b) *o*-CHLOROBENZALIDINETHIOSEMICARBAZONE

No.	Ni(II) taken (mg)	Ni(II) complex (mg)		Ni(II) found (mg)		% error	
		(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
1.	10	86.00	83.90	10.01	10.01	+0.10	+0.10
2.	20	172.10	168.00	20.04	20.03	+0.20	+0.15
3.	30	257.10	252.00	30.05	30.04	+0.16	+0.13

Pd(II) is precipitated with these reagents at pH=2-3 hence it can be separated from nickel at this pH range. Cu(II) is precipitated as blackish brown ppt. at pH=6-8 hence it interferes. The interference can be avoided by the addition of potassium tartarate. Co(II) is not precipitated by the reagents. Fe(III) is also prevented to precipitate by using potassium tartarate as masking agent. Thus Ni(II) (20 mg) can be determined in the presence of 10mg of Cu(II) or Fe(III), the maximum error being 1%.

Structure of the Chelates :—Ortho-substituted benzalidine-thiosemicarbazones behave as bidentate ligands in neutral, ammoniacal and acid media. The chemical analysis of the complexes indicate that they have the chemical formula(I). Ni(C₈H₇N₄O₂S)₂ (Found : C-38%, H-2.60%, N-22%, Ni-11.60%, Calculated : C-38.04%, H-2.78%, N-22.20%, Ni-11.63%). (II) Ni(C₈H₇N₄SCl)₂ (Found : C-39.70%, H-2.80%, N-17.20%, Ni-12.10%, Calculated : C-39.60%, H-2.90%, H-2.90%, N-17.36%, Ni-12.14%).

The complexes are diamagnetic. Their acetone solns. show maximum absorption band at about 15000 cm⁻¹. The magnetic behaviour and electronic spectra² suggest for square planar structure of the complexes. The I.R. spectra of the complexes have been recorded to determine the nature of bonding in the complexes. The presence of a sharp band at about 5050 cm⁻¹ both in the ligands

and complexes indicates that N-H frequency remains unchanged in the complexes. The decrease in stretching³⁻⁵ frequency from about 720-730 cm⁻¹ in the ligands to 630-640 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicates M-S bonding. The presence of new bands at about 500 cm⁻¹ and 450 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicate the coordination through N and S. The presence of the bands at 830 cm⁻¹ and 1380 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of uncoordinated nitrite group⁶. It was not possible to get any information regarding the co-ordination of chlorine as I.R. spectra were recorded between 4000 cm⁻¹ and 400 cm⁻¹ only.

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Semi-Micro Titrimetric Estimation of Silver(I) Using N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-Cysteine*

P. DHAR and G. N. MUKHERJEE**

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

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SILVER can be estimated by a number of titrimetric methods^{1,2} involving precipitation, complexation, etc. All these are based on the low solubilities of silver halides and/or pseudohalides. Some of these methods require accurate control of proper pH values particularly for the action of the indicators used. The present communication describes a method in which silver has been estimated on the semi-micro scale by acid-base titration using the ligand N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-Cysteine [NBSC or

C₆H₅SO₂NHCH(COOH)CH₂SH or HS-LH-COOH]. The amount of alkali required to titrate silver(I) solution containing some free mineral acid using phenol-red indicator represents the total amount of free acid only. When a solution of mono-sodium salt of the ligand, HSLHCOONa, is added providing sufficient excess to this titrated solution one equivalent of acid per gram-atom of silver is liberated due to deprotonation the thiol (-SH) group of the ligand by silver(I) according to the stoichiometry:

Titration with alkali is continued and the amount of alkali required at this stage to reach a just red end point gives the amount of silver(I) present. The amount of silver was calculated using the factor 1 ml of (N) NaOH solution \equiv 107.9 mg of Ag.

Experimental

(a) Reagent Solution:

A 2% solution of monosodium salt (HSLHCOONa) of NBSC was used as the reagent. This was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of the ligand NBSC^{2,3} in water and neutralising the solution with carbonate-free NaOH using phenol red indicator^{1b}. 10-15 ml of this solution was used for each titration of 6-60 mg of silver.

(b) Procedure:

Aliquots (containing 6-60 mg of silver) of a standard AgClO₄ solution were diluted nearly to 100 ml and phenol red indicator^{1b} (3 drops) was added and the resulting solution was titrated with a carbonate free standard (\approx 0.30 M) sodium hydroxide solution to a just red colour. The amount of alkali required was equivalent to the amount of free mineral acid present in the AgClO₄ solution. 10-15 ml of the reagent solution was then added. Colour of the solution changed to yellow and a white solid, AgSLHCOOH, (confirmed by analysis and i.r. study on isolation) was precipitated. Titration with alkali was continued, the solid compound redissolved during the course of titration. Amount of alkali required at this stage to get a just-red end point gave the amount of silver present in the solution. The results of the estimations are recorded in Table I.

(c) Interferences:

Substances which oxidise the ligand and/or reduce Ag(I) interfere. Metal ions such as Hg(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Bi(III), Pb(II), Pt(II), Pd(II), which form complexes with the ligand and Fe(III), Al(III) of which hydroxides are precipitated below or within the experimental pH range interfere. Fe(III) up to 15% can be

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** Senior author, for correspondence.